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Pastoral Counseling and Its Impacts on Selected Rehabilitation Centres of the Redeemed Christian Church of God in Ogun State Nigeria

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Abstract

Pastoral counselling is a form of counselling that integrates spiritual and religious beliefs into the therapeutic process. The Redeemed Christian Church of God (RCCG) being a religious organisation, incorporates pastoral counselling into its rehabilitation centres to support the recovery process of individuals struggling with addiction or other issues of life. Previous studies on Pastoral counselling have been without a critical examination of its impacts on the rehabilitation of individuals to determine its social influence or otherwise. Hence this paper explores pastoral counseling and its impacts on selected rehabilitation centers of the Redeemed Christian Church of God in Ogun State Nigeria. This research utilizes a qualitative approach including interviews and observations, to gather data and analyse the impacts of pastoral counseling. The study aims to assess the effectiveness of pastoral counselling in facilitating the rehabilitation process and improving the overall well-being of individuals seeking help in the centres. It was discovered from the findings that pastoral counselling had a significant impact on people in rehabilitation, as it addresses not only the individual's mental and emotional well-being but also the dynamics and relationships within the rehabilitation unit. These findings contribute to the understanding of the significance of pastoral counselling in rehabilitation centres and provide insights for further improvement in the field.

Keywords: Pastoral Counseling, Rehabilitation Centres, The Redeemed Christian Church of God, Ogun State, Nigeria

Introduction

Pastoral counselling is a form of counselling that integrates spiritual resources and beliefs into the counselling process (Ayegba, 2015). It aims to provide emotional and psychological support to individuals who are facing various challenges in life (Adeniran, 2017). In recent years, pastoral counselling has gained popularity as an effective approach to addressing mental health issues and supporting personal growth and development.

This research paper focuses on the impacts of pastoral counselling on selected rehabilitation centres of the Redeemed Christian Church of God in Ogun State, Nigeria. The Redeemed Christian Church of God is one of the largest and fastest-growing churches in Nigeria, with a strong focus on the well-being and spiritual growth of its members (Oyewumi, 2019). The church operates several rehabilitation centres across the country, providing support and care for individuals struggling with substance abuse, mental health issues, and other challenges.

The purpose of this research is to explore the efficacy of pastoral counselling in the rehabilitation centres of the Redeemed Christian Church of God in Ogun State. This study

investigates the experiences of individuals who have received pastoral counselling in these centres, as well as the perceptions of the counsellors and staff members involved in the counselling process. By examining the impacts of pastoral counselling on the rehabilitation centre, this research aims to contribute to the growing body of knowledge on the effectiveness of this approach in addressing mental health issues and promoting well-being.

To support this research, a comprehensive review of relevant literature on pastoral counselling, mental health, and rehabilitation will be conducted. The theoretical framework for the study will be grounded in the principles of pastoral counselling and the unique context of the Redeemed Christian Church of God in Nigeria. Data will be collected through interviews, surveys, and observational methods, and analyzed using qualitative research techniques.

Overall, this research paper seeks to shed light on the role of pastoral counselling in promoting mental health and well-being in rehabilitation centres, particularly within the context of the Redeemed Christian Church of God in Ogun State, Nigeria. The findings of this study will have implications for the development of effective counselling programmes and interventions in similar settings, as well as for the broader field of pastoral counselling and mental health care.

Overview of Pastoral Counseling

Generally, counselling means discussion, advice, exchange of ideas, consultation, or decision-making process. Counselling is a service designed to help individuals analyze themselves by relating their abilities, achievements, interests, and ways of adapting to new decisions they have made or need to make (Neukrug, 2018). This service is central to a rehabilitation counsellor's work. While other aspects of rehabilitation may concern the provision and interpretation of information, counselling is concerned with a person's feelings, attitudes, and emotional dispositions about themselves and the situations they face. In other words, advising is when an advisor develops a dialogic relationship to help people better understand themselves concerning current and future decisions and issues. Makinde in the words of Roger describes counselling as a series of direct contacts with individuals aimed at assisting in changing attitudes and behaviours. Makinde, further writes that "effective counselling" consists of a structured and tolerant relationship in which the client gains self-understanding to the extent that he or she can consider changing direction and taking positive steps. Masu Arbuckle states that the general purpose of counselling is to help the person free himself from the entanglement and disempowerment of tentacles so that he can be his authentic self and contribute more to himself and those around him (Gladding, 2018).

In the same sense, pastoral counselling is a form of psychotherapy that combines both psychology and spirituality. It is provided by certified pastoral counsellors, who are not only mental health professionals but who have also had in-depth religious and/or theological training. The goal of pastoral counselling is to help individuals overcome emotional, psychological and spiritual challenges by integrating their faith into the therapeutic process. Pastoral counsellors use a variety of techniques to help their clients, including prayer, meditation, and other spiritual practices.

Pastoral counselling can be beneficial for individuals who are struggling with a wide range of issues, including depression, anxiety, grief, addiction, and relationship problems. It can also be helpful for individuals who are seeking guidance on how to live a more fulfilling life or who are looking for support during a difficult time.

Selected Rehabilitation Centers of the Redeemed Christian Church of God in Ogun State Nigeria

Rehabilitation Centers of the Redeemed Christian Church of God in Ogun State selected for this study are two out of 5 because of easy accessibility to the researcher including:

1) The Habitation of Hope Rehabilitation Centre

The Habitation of Hope Rehabilitation Centre is a faith-based organisation run by the Redeemed Christian Church of God (RCCG) that provides rehabilitation and support services for individuals struggling with addiction and other behavioural issues. The RCCG recognized the growing problem of addiction and substance abuse in society and the need for a comprehensive rehabilitation programme. In response to this, the church established the Habitation of Hope Rehabilitation Centre as a solution to the prevailing societal challenges (Olowe & Olusanya, (2014). It was founded in 2006 to take care of juvenile drug addicts and street children between the ages of 7 to 17years old. The rehabilitation centre has over 180 boys, 40% of which are in private secondary schools. There is also a primary school within the rehabilitation centre for the younger ones. Others who are not academically inclined are into various vocational activities like tailoring, shoe making, carpentry, and computer training.

The centre aims to offer a supportive and structured environment to help individuals recover and rebuild their lives. It employs a holistic approach that combines spiritual guidance, counselling, medical care, vocational training, and life skills development. The Habitation of Hope Rehabilitation Centre of RCCG believes in the power of faith and prayer in the recovery process. It offers daily devotions, Bible studies, and church services to help individuals strengthen their spiritual well-being. The centre was founded on the principles of the Christian faith, with the belief that true freedom from addiction can only be achieved through a personal relationship with Jesus Christ. Overall, the Habitation of Hope Rehabilitation Centre of RCCG aims to provide a safe and nurturing environment for individuals to heal and transform their lives.

2) Wholistic Outreach Rehabilitation Centre

The Wholistic Outreach Rehabilitation Centre of the Redeemed Christian Church of God, (RCCG) was founded in April 2002 as a result of the moral decadence in society, reflected in the horde of commercial sex workers, increase in numbers of pregnant and stranded teenagers, neglected young girls and ladies in various stages of destitution who are all suffering from the effect of drug addiction. The organization offers social services for female youth and women who are between the ages of 16 to 50, both within and outside the Church (RCCG) in various communities.

It is a faith-based non-profit organization founded upon Christian values and principles, committed to reducing harms associated with prostitution and other accompanying activities. It

is located in Mowe, Ogun State, in Southwestern Nigeria. The centre models God's love and purity to a generation of youths and brings hope, love, and succour to them. Rehabilitation strategies at the centre include the use of capacity-building, income-generating activities, the scriptures and pastoral counselling as a means to behavioural change to checkmate problems like HIV/AIDS/STIs/STDs and unwanted pregnancy in society. The organization offers social services and promotes women's development both within and outside the Church and in various communities to prove the sacredness of life, especially that of females and in developing the country.

Major Types of Pastoral Counselling in RCCG Rehabilitation Centres

The three major types of Pastoral counselling that were identified in the rehabilitation centres include individual, group and family counselling:

1) **Individual Counselling:** This counselling is scheduled to take place a minimum of once a week but some of them may have daily individual sessions when special needs arise. During individual counselling, the clients meet in one-on-one sessions with the counsellor. These sessions are private and generally last about an hour. During individual counselling, the counsellor explores the client's background to find the root causes for the drug addiction and other behavioural issues. Then, the counsellor and the beneficiaries work together to ensure that the beneficiaries receive all the tools and coping skills needed for a life of recovery and enable each of them to deal with issues that they prefer not to deal with in a group setting (Interview:13/10/2023).

2) **Group Counselling:** This is done three times per week at the various centres. Here, the recovering person also meets with fellow clients in a group counselling session. These sessions are all about sharing experiences and providing support for one another. This process can be intimidating at first, however, the sheer release of talking to other people who have been through the same experiences provides an amazing relief. This group counselling focused on a particular issue, for example, obsessive-compulsive disorder or anger management. While the counsellor usually harmonises the contributions from each member of the group that are considered valuable because, most of them in the group share similar issues, feelings, defences and differences are addressed. Each person learns how to express emotion openly and to trust others. Here, everyone feels comfortable, safe and relaxed knowing that they are with people who are going through similar experiences (Interview: 13/10/2023).

3) Family Counselling

This is done at the beginning and the end of the rehabilitation programmes. Here, the addicts are allowed to have an open and honest discussion with their family members, parents and siblings. It is believed that when an individual develops a drug addiction with its accompanied behavioural problems, they are not the only one who suffers. Often, the addict's family suffers right along with them, and in many ways can even have a more difficult time than the addicts themselves. Therefore, counsellors provide family members with strategies that will help the recovering addict stay on the right path when they leave the rehabilitation centres. Parish

ministers with skills in counselling and theological education are called upon to counsel individual addicts as part of their shepherding mandate (Interview: 13/10/2023)

Impacts of Pastoral Counseling on Rehabilitation Centers of the Redeemed Christian Church of God in Ogun State, Nigeria

1. Emotional and Spiritual Healing: Pastoral counselling within the RCCG Rehabilitation Centre offers emotional and spiritual support to individuals undergoing rehabilitation. Their counselling sessions for example in Wholistic Outreach Rehabilitation Centre, aim to address the underlying issues and traumas that may have contributed to addiction or other challenges, thereby helping individuals gain emotional and support healing. Pastoral counselling provides a safe and non-judgmental space for individuals to express their emotions, fears, and struggles. The counselling process provides an enabling environment for them to address underlying issues contributing to their addiction or mental health challenges.

2. Integration of Faith: RCCG's pastoral counselling incorporates the principles of the Christian faith, including prayer, scripture-based guidance, and support from pastors or trained counsellors (Interview: 14/10/2023) This integration helps individuals in the two rehabilitation centres to find strength, hope, and a sense of purpose through their faith, which is a powerful motivator for recovery.

3. A sense of Community and peer support: The RCCG Rehabilitation Centre aims to provide a supportive community for individuals seeking rehabilitation, and pastoral counselling plays a significant role in fostering this sense of community and peer support (Observation:16/10/2023). Group counselling sessions and activities in the Habitation of Hope and Wholistic Outreach Rehabilitation Centre led by pastors or trained counsellors promote a supportive environment where individual clients share their experiences, learn from one another, and build meaningful relationships.

4. Personal Transformation: Pastoral counselling in the RCCG Rehabilitation centres empowers individual clients/rehabilitators to undergo a journey of personal transformation (Interview:16/10/2023). By addressing issues such as guilt, shame, self-worth and forgiveness, counselling sessions equip individual' clients with the tools necessary to make positive changes in their lives and develop healthier habits.

The integration of spiritual principles in pastoral counselling in these centres allows individuals to explore their faith and find meaning in their lives. This spiritual guidance fosters a sense of purpose and helps individuals develop a stronger connection with their God as written in 1 Corinthians 5:17, thereby leading to transformation and personal growth.

5. Aftercare Support: Pastoral counselling extends beyond the duration of the rehabilitation programmes, as the RCCG rehabilitation centre is dedicated to providing comprehensive aftercare support (Intervie:16/10/2023). This support often includes continued counselling, spiritual guidance, and access to resources that can enhance long-term recovery and prevent relapse (Adeyemi, 2015).

Conclusion

Pastoral counselling plays a significant role in the rehabilitation process in the two centres of the Redeemed Christian Church of God in Ogun State, Nigeria selected for this study. The impacts of pastoral counselling include Emotional and Spiritual Healing, Integration of Faith, A sense of Community and peer support, personal transformation, and Aftercare Support. This paper highlights the importance of integrating pastoral counselling in rehabilitation centres and provides insights for further improvement in the field.

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